

Refining Scenario Reporting: Developing a Glossary for Enhanced Interpretability and Replicability in Scenario-Based Research

David Myrén

Katastrofmedicinskt centrum
Internationella Medicinska programmet

Abstract

Much effort has been put into the definitions of terms relevant to scenario-based research and descriptions in the design phase of scenarios. This study builds on this earlier research, but instead examines how scenarios should be described in reports and papers. The motivation is that descriptions in scientific and governmental reports are often lacking or use field-specific terminology to describe critical elements. These issues lead to reduced interpretability within and between organizations and a reduced ability to replicate studies. This in turn leads to less effective policy-making and inter-organizational cooperation. This study performed a qualitative analysis of how organizations think about scenarios in an attempt to extract a terminology that bridges the qualitative and quantitative gaps that often exist in how scenarios are used between organizations. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 9 participants from 6 different fields. From the interviews a glossary was created containing 9 categories (*General Definitions, Scenario types, Scenario components, Design attributes, Roles, Evaluation and outcomes, Temporal dynamics, Immersion mechanics, Logistics and tools*) and 46 terms. The purpose of the glossary is to bring to light elements that are necessary to describe in some detail in order to create a full description of what makes up a specific scenario. Two proposed applications of the glossary are suggested. Firstly, as a checklist for scenarists to make sure that all individual elements in the description are covered. Secondly, as a tool to increase communication between organizations. Further research should focus on validating the glossary by comparing it with additional organizations such as the military, fields that employ virtual scenarios, and other high-complexity settings.

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1 Introduction

Scenario usage in research is at the fundamental level the study of macro- and joint cognition, often in complex systems, usually between multiple humans or humans and technology (Miller, 2010). Macrocognition is the study of cognition in real-world settings, as opposed to a controlled laboratory setting. More specifically, it studies naturalistic decision making, adaptation, planning, problem detection, and more (Klein et al., 2003). Joint cognition, on the other hand, studies which mental abilities are used and how they are used when people work in a group setting (Towse et al., 2016). Scenarios in research and government settings are also generally considered to be aimed at the future (Spaniol & Rowland, 2019). Many different research fields (psychology, cognitive science, human factors, future and foresight, etc.), professional fields (security companies, oil and mining companies, etc.), and governmental bodies (the military, police, the fire department, etc.) use scenarios for evaluation (exploratory), exercise (normative), and knowledge generation (predictive). An outlier is the game design industry that uses scenarios to create entertainment. It is also used in future and forecast research. The fact that scenarios are used for many different reasons and (mostly) as a way to prepare for the future suggests that the process of creating them is inherently dynamic. One of these dynamic parts is the terminology, and other qualitative and quantitative dimensions shift depending on current demands.

Each of these fields approaches scenarios differently and understands them in different ways that fit their needs (Quade & Boucher, 1968). Variations can include scale in terms of agents involved (quantitative difference), level of reality ranging from table-top exercises, computer simulations, to full-scale war games with real soldiers and technology (qualitative difference). This means that terminology can shift between and even within fields. The multiple motivations for using scenarios also mean that terminology, description, design process, data collection, and analysis can vary. Most of these variations do not necessarily create qualitative issues, as each individual scenario demands different approaches. However, it can create communication, coordination, and epistemological problems.

1.1 Background

The issue of terminology has been discussed by (Spaniol & Rowland, 2019) in a study refuting what has been called a definition confusion in future and forecast science. In this paper, Spaniol and Rowland suggest a definition of what a scenario is that is composed of individual parts of preexisting definitions. In their study, Spaniol and Rowland examined 77 existing definitions of what a scenario is and found significant similarities between them. They found that the five most used descriptive words were; future, possible, plausible, story and event. This analysis confirms the multiplicity of interpretations and applications of scenarios between disciplines and contexts while still showcasing the multitude of interpretations that exist. Another study by (Bishop et al., 2007) examined the different techniques that exist in scenario development to define what scenario development actually is.

While the studies by Spaniol, Rowland, and Bishop et al. focus on issues related to *definitions* in scenarios, the present study will focus on the *description* of them. The rationale behind this is that missing variables or characteristics in the description of a scenario can create issues such as replication and interpretation of results. Brief, high-level descriptions might be sufficient for low-complexity small-scale scenarios. But it becomes more salient to cover all details the larger the scale and importance of the scenario, where small variations in the scenario design might lead to vastly different results. The effect of these variations or misunderstandings could potentially have economic effects, lead to accidents, misallocated resources due to misleading interpretations of the results, and negative impacts on decision and policy making.

Another motivation is that many fields cooperate to different degrees; for example, the police department needs to cooperate with the fire department and paramedics when there is a traffic accident.

When these organizations are trying to improve their operations and develop it to meet future needs by using scenarios, they sometimes need to consider other organizations on which they are interdependent in some capacity. That is, they need to understand how the other organization thinks and functions, including legal mandates and available resources. This can be done by exchanging information with each other or performing joint scenarios.

Cross-organizational cooperation is a mode of operations that is requested to become more common, the Swedish government has requested that the police and Swedish armed forces deepen their cooperation (Ministry of Justice, 2023), to name one example. If organizations have a shared terminology, it could help facilitate and improve intensified cooperation and produce better results. The reason why a shared understanding of terminology is important is that language is one of the key factors in creating shared mental models between people (Andrews et al., 2022). A shared mental model (or team mental model in larger groups) allows individuals to negotiate, communicate, ask clarifying questions, and establish a common ground more easily (Klimoski & Mohammed, 1994).

1.2 Scenario descriptions

Describing scenarios can be done in many different ways, ranging from formalized models that use statistical models to produce events and sequences to experience-based approaches. An example of a formalized approach is the CIA-ISM (Bañuls, Turoff, & Hiltz, 2013). It is used to determine cascading and codependent effects of individual events with the aim of creating as realistic scenarios as possible. Realistic in this context refers to how probable the included events are and how probable the sequence of events are. This method is designed to be used for emergency preparedness scenarios and is focused on how social factors impact each other. It allows scenarists to estimate the likelihood of each event and how much each event impacts other events. The other approach described in a paper by (Murakami et al., 2003) instead focuses on how to describe interactions between individual agents in the best possible way. It is a coarse-grain, multi-agent simulation tool that allows scenarists to apply different behavior to each individual that takes part in the scenario. The tool lets the scenarists formalize actions that individuals can take in a given event and then model the interactions between individuals depending on their assigned actions. Both approaches deal with social interactions. But they differ in one important way: CIA-ISM is focused on estimating probabilities between interactions, while the method described by Murakami et al. is focused on describing single actions taken by individual agents and formalizing them so that they can be transferred to a digital simulation software. These description approaches mainly focus on how to describe elements while constructing and planning the scenario. This study aims to create a tool to improve descriptions of scenarios in reports after the scenario has been held.

1.3 Purpose and Research Question

This study aims to create a glossary on how to describe scenarios in scientific articles and other reports. The purpose of this will be to assist researchers in reporting and describing their scenarios more exhaustively. The motivation is to improve the quality of scenario descriptions in scientific studies and, in addition, to improve the robustness and validity of scenario-based research.

The glossary will be created through the research question: How can scenario terminology and descriptions be refined to account for qualitative as well as quantitative differences between research fields?

2 Method

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with professional scenarists. The interview questions were extracted from a brief review of the literature on definitions and descriptions of scenarios.

The interviews were conducted individually, except in one case with 9 professionals from 4 different fields, 2 nurses (interviewed together), 1 firefighter, 1 regional exercise coordinator at the Swedish police, 1 live action role-play organizer, 1 security senior advisor with a background in the Swedish military, and lastly 3 disaster and traumatology physicians working with planning and analyzing exercises. The professionals were instructors, analysts, or scenario designers.

2.1 Interview protocol

The participants were all given the same set of questions (see Appendix 1) and were informed of the purpose of the study before the interview began. Before starting the interview, participants were also asked for their consent to record the interview. They were also informed that the interviews would be anonymous, and that no personal information would be used. The interview was designed to go from high to low level of detail. Furthermore, the interview was divided into 10 sections with 2 to 3 questions in each section focusing on a specific topic (see Appendix 1).

2.2 Recruitment and sampling

The participants were recruited by the researcher and the supervisor. The sampling was purposeful to target participants from different professional and vocational fields to provide a wider range of answers. The participants were contacted by email explaining the purpose of the interview and the reason they were contacted.

2.3 Data collection

All interviews except one took place digitally on Microsoft Teams, and the interview that was not done digitally was done in person. The longest interview was 82 minutes, and the other six ranged between 54 and 64 minutes. The reason why one interview took 82 minutes was that the two nurses were interviewed together at their request. The video and audio of the interviews were recorded and saved. The audio files were automatically transcribed into text using Microsoft Teams, then monitored against the recorded sound file to ensure that the transcription was correct.

2.4 Data analysis

The semi-structured interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. The codes relevant to the research goal of each interview were gathered from the transcription. The codes were extracted using a combination of semantic and latent approaches (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Finally, the codes were turned into terms and matched together into categories.

2.5 Materials

Microsoft Teams was used to perform, record and transcribe the interviews.

Google Docs was used to create the interview questionnaire, analyze the transcriptions, and extract codes and themes.

3 Results

From the interviews 9 categories and 46 terms were identified. The categories were General Definitions, Scenario types, Scenario components, Design attributes, Roles, Evaluation and outcomes, Temporal dynamics, Immersion mechanics, Logistics and tools. Each category and term represent one dimension that at least one participant explicitly mentioned or were found through the latent analysis. In the following section, the categories and selected key terms are presented in more detail. The full glossary can be found in Appendix 2.

3.1 General definitions

General definitions include the overarching terms that guide the design of the scenario at every level, and also influence each other in some way. For example, the goal and the purpose guide each other. Each can be defined first, but they are always interlinked. They also influence how the scenario is designed. Most terms in this category had a shared understanding between all participants; for example, they all made a difference between a scenario and an exercise. The hierarchical relationship between exercise and scenario differed to some degree. Most of the participants claimed that the scenario is what frames the exercise in time, space, and purpose, while others thought of the exercise as the overarching structure where the scenario drives the exercise forward. An exercise includes a purpose and a goal, but not necessarily a scenario. For example, participant 3 mentioned that nurses can perform intubation exercises or other tasks without the necessity of doing it within a larger context (scenario). It was also unanimously considered that the scenario is something that is created, it does not exist.

3.2 Scenario types

Scenarios can be done in many different ways and with multiple purposes, from full-scale scenarios with real equipment, tools, and other physical artifacts to table-top and recreational scenarios. The purpose and resources typically guide the type of scenario that is chosen according to the participants.

3.3 Scenario components

Scenarios can be broken down into individual parts that change for each scenario so that it's goal and purpose can be satisfied. Not every scenario or organization use the same components even though there was a significant overlap between the participants in which components they mentioned and discussed. Intrigues for example are mostly used in Live-action role-playing. Whereas narratives were mentioned in every type of scenario and by all participants. This was the category with most terms (9).

3.4 Temporal dynamics

As scenarios are sequenced events, they have a temporal dimension that potentially influence the participants in different ways and in turn, the outcomes of a scenario. A chronological, real-time scenario-design aimed at testing a hospitals capability of managing an extended crisis will see different outcomes compared to a scenario design that is chronological but utilize time compression to test different stages of the crisis in a single day. They also have practical and logistical value, such as at what time of the day should the scenario start and how much time is needed to complete the scenario.

3.5 Immersion mechanisms

Many of the interview participants mentioned the importance of creating immersion in the scenario participants. Participant 1, 2, 3 and 8 mentioned explicitly that they want their scenario participants to enter an “exercise bubble” and that it is an important factor for a scenario to be successful. The other participants also mentioned immersion but less explicitly. Immersion can be created through the narrative, props, events or other triggers such as videos and images. Immersion is created by creating a realistic scenario according to the participants.

3.6 Design attributes

These are similar to Scenario Components but are more conceptual in nature. They guide which Scenario Components that will be used in designing the scenario. Realism is a key concept that all scenarists need to think about in the design phase. The interviewed scenarists discussed the importance of deep domain knowledge to create realistic scenarios. Mostly personal and organizational experience was used to determine events, participants, location and other components of the scenario to make it realistic. The participants discussed that the goal and purpose typically guide the level of realism that is chosen but resources such as available participants, financial resources and material resources also plays a role. Realism was discussed on three different levels by the participants. The three kinds were: physical realism, as in the scenario is played out in the appropriate environment using the correct physical artifacts. Another kind of realism is simulated or abstract realism, as in the environment, social and organizational structure is abstractly but correctly represented using whiteboards, maps, board games, or other representations. The third kind of realism is how probable the scenario is, meaning how realistic the event sequence, communication modes, procedures and the effects of the actions that the participants take are.

3.7 Roles

This category describes the different roles defined by the interview participants. Participants are those who act inside the scenario and usually “act” their professional role. The counterpart role are people that can either fill missing functions or act as adversaries. The remaining roles relate to those who organize, lead and create the scenario. All participants mentioned all roles included in the glossary and defined them in the same way. The non-participatory roles often overlap with people filling multiple roles, such as the Facilitator usually design and construct the scenario as well. This role was given a few different titles in the interview apart from facilitator, game master, moderator, scenario moderator and narrator were mentioned.

3.8 Evaluation and outcomes

All scenarios are evaluated in some way. In exercise-focused scenarios the participants performance can be evaluated or the performance of the scenario itself can be evaluated to examine if it was able to fulfill the purpose and goal. To do the evaluation the interview participants mentioned a few different methods. Some use more structured and formal tools such as After Action Review. It is a tool that lets the user compare the wanted outcome and the outcome that the scenario produced (Cronin & Andrews, 2009). The interviewed scenarists also mentioned that outcomes can be surprising and emergent, depending on how the scenario is structured. For these kinds of outcomes participant 2 highlighted that it is important to be careful when reporting these outcomes and contextualize why they might have occurred.

3.9 Logistics and tools

This category describes the kind of tools used by the scenarists before, during and after the scenario has been held. The tools mentioned range from pen and paper to simulation software. How the scenario was planned differed between the participants from using preexisting guides and templates to using their own earlier experience and organizational experience. The most common method to plan or create the scenario was a combination of official guidelines and reusing or drawing inspiration from earlier scenarios.

4 Discussion

The evolution of language is inevitable, and possibly even more so in organizations that are involved in preparing for the future. This implies that there needs to be flexibility in the design process since scenarios are used to represent the future. This means that new components might be added or discovered while others will be made obsolete. The wide range of different types of organizations that use scenarios also makes it difficult to create a unified list of definitions. Lastly, these factors also make it difficult and potentially counterproductive to create strict templates or guidelines on how to plan a scenario. However, the descriptions of the scenarios must be detailed enough so that analysts, evaluators, and other relevant third parties can get a clear and full view of why the scenario produced a certain outcome and how these outcomes were identified.

The glossary produced in this study is an attempt to collect the key individual elements (terms) that are necessary to include in a scenario description to create this clear and full view. Many of the elements are likely familiar to many scenarists as most of the included terms were explicitly mentioned by the participants. The remaining elements were implicitly mentioned by at least one participant and extracted through thematic analysis. This potentially indicates that there is a shared understanding of what makes up a scenario. However, some elements had different interpretations between the participants. One of these elements is realism. Realism is broken down into three types. Simulated, physical, and believable realism. These types can be thought about more or less consciously in each organization. All participants discussed the importance of creating a realistic scenario in some way, but not all levels were explicitly mentioned by all participants. The most mentioned type of realism was what the glossary calls “simulated” or “abstract” realism (derived from the interviews). This element describes how the scenario abstractly represents physical artifacts, environments, and other system-specific features. This type of realism is mostly connected to table-top or discussion-based scenarios, although it most likely exists to some degree in all types of scenarios. The sampling of the participants might have influenced this finding, as 5 of 9 participants mainly plan scenarios that focus on the systemic and organizational level of analysis. An interesting discovery in the thematic analysis was the similarity between the way the LARP participant described scenarios and scenario planning to the other fields. Most of the terms mentioned by the participants in the other fields were also mentioned by the LARP-creator. The main differences were that the LARP-creator mentioned terms such as “bleed” and “safety mechanisms,” while the other participants did not mention this explicitly. The other participants discussed safety as in that the scenarios are used to improve the safety of the scenario participants when they perform tasks in real world situations.

4.1 Use cases for the glossary

When it comes to the application and purpose of the glossary. It can be viewed as a sort of checklist when writing scenario reports and possibly as a tool for improved cooperation between organizations. By making the categories and terms more visible and salient it could help scenarists produce more exhaustive reports. It might also reduce the mental workload required by the scenarist when writing their report. The glossary potentially also makes it easier to create a shared mental model and a shared understanding between organizations if they have an explicit vocabulary to refer to during discussions and other cooperative activities.

The exact definitions of the terms may change over time, and, as mentioned previously, new ones might be created, and others made obsolete. The categories, on the other hand, may be general enough to be reused over time.

4.2 Limitations

One limitation of the study is that the questionnaire may have influenced the categories and terms that were able to be identified. A questionnaire with different questions may be able to identify additional or

different items for the glossary. Another limitation is that the study was unable to include an interview with a participant active in the military. The military might be considered the most experienced organization when it comes to conducting exercises and planning scenarios. By including them, the results of the study might be more reliable and exhaustive. Further validation of the results, for example, by having independent professional scenarists review the glossary, may also benefit the validity of the study. This was not done due to time constraints.

4.3 Future studies

One suggestion for future studies is to compare the glossary produced in this study with the way the military describes scenarios. Another is to more thoroughly compare scenario descriptions between scenarios held in a research setting and scenarios held by governmental and other organizations.

5 Conclusion

The goal of this study was to extract key concepts and elements used by professional scenarists in the creation, performance, and evaluation of scenarios. The purpose was to create a template or glossary meant to support scenarists in their reporting. In conclusion, this study has shown that there is a large overlap in Swedish organizations in how they think about scenarios and in how they describe them, but that there are individual differences in which terms and categories are used the most. If the glossary proves comprehensive, its positive implications could be improved reporting of scenarios, leading to improved quality in scenario-based research. It might also improve organizational decision making and policy making, as they will have better data to guide their thinking.

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7 Appendix

7.1 Appendix 1 - Interview Questions

1. Vad är ett scenario för er?
 - Hur definierar ni ett scenario inom er organisation?
 - Är det skillnad mellan övning och scenario? Finns det en relation mellan dem?
 - Vilka ord använder ni för att beskriva scenariot?
2. Hur/Varför används scenarier?
 - Vad är syftet med scenarierna i er verksamhet?
 - Skapar, designar eller bygger ni scenariot? Finns det en specifik vokabulär i organisationen för detta? SBAR
 - Inspiration: Tre typer av scenarier:
 - Vad kommer hända?
 - Vad kan hända?
 - Hur kan ett specifikt mål uppnås?
3. Hur bestäms vad som ska ingå i scenariot?
 - Hur bestäms vilka faktorer eller inslag som ska ingå i scenariot? (Exempel: deltagare, miljö, resurser)
 - Kopplas dessa inslag till vad som mäts eller analyseras?
 - Vilka dimensioner ramar in scenariot, t.ex. deltagare, geografisk plats, tidsdimension?
 - Hur tar ni hänsyn till nivåer av analys, t.ex. grupp- vs individperspektiv? Vad mäts/utvärderas/utvecklas?
 - Har ni några nyckelfaktorer ni utgår ifrån när ni bygger ett scenario?
4. Användning av verktyg och ramverk
 - Använder ni några mallar eller ramverk för att bygga era scenarier?
 - Använder ni några digitala eller fysiska verktyg i designfasen, t.ex. AI, Excel, 3D- simulatorer?
 - Använder ni er av narrativ eller storytelling? Hur utvecklas det i så fall?
5. Hur dokumenteras och analyseras scenarier?
 - Hur dokumenteras scenariot?
 - Hur bestämmer ni hur komplex övningen ska vara, och hur bedömer ni att den är tillräckligt komplex för att ge de resultat ni vill ha?
 - Hur "verklighetstroga" är era scenarier? Är det table-top-övningar, 3D-simulatorer, rollspel? Hur mycket bygger ni scenarierna på verkliga fakta?
 - Hur hanteras tid- och rumsförändringar i scenariot? T.ex. hoppar ni i tid mellan scenariots delar eller kör ni linjärt?
6. Roller och ansvar i scenariot
 - Vilka roller finns för de som är delaktiga i scenariot (skapare, deltagare, instruktörer)?
 - Hur ser spelorganisationen ut? Vem ansvarar för scenarioledning och design?
 - Hur aktiveras alla deltagare under scenariots gång?
7. Deltagare och resurser

- Hur bestäms och dokumenteras antalet deltagare i scenariot? Är det ett specifikt antal eller spelar det mindre roll?
 - Hur bestämmer ni vilka som ska delta?
 - Hur bestämmer ni vilka resurser som ska finnas tillgängliga, t.ex. verktyg, fordon, teknik? Hur dokumenteras detta?
8. Start- och slutpunkter i övningen
- Hur bestämmer ni startpunkt och slutpunkt för övningen?
 - Dokumenteras och presenteras detta i rapporter?
9. Presentation och rapportering av scenarier
- Hur visualiserar, presenterar eller beskriver ni scenariot i rapporter och för deltagarna? Använder ni er av narrativ?
 - Hur dokumenterar och rapporterar ni utfallet av ett scenario?
 - Hur tänker ni kring relationen mellan utfall och scenario?
10. Övningsavdelning och ansvar
- Finns det en specifik avdelning i organisationen som ansvarar för att skapa och leda scenarier?

7.2 Appendix 2 – Glossary

Categories	Terms	Definitions
General Definitions	Scenario (Scenario)	A structured representation of a possible future event or process defining the world, organizational roles, and context.
	Exercise (Övning)	Activities set up to test or improve capabilities. Often exists inside a scenario but not necessarily.
	Purpose (Syfte)	Why the scenario or exercise is held.
	Goal (Mål)	What the scenario or exercise is meant to produce and/or achieve.
Scenario Types	Table-top Scenario (Diskussionsövning)	Abstract, often discussion-based scenarios focusing on decisionmaking and planning. Usually on organizational or systemic level.
	Full-Scale Scenario (Fullskaligt scenario)	Immersive scenarios replicating real-world conditions with high resource use.
	Normative Scenario (Testandeövning)	Scenarios designed to evaluate specific systems, tools, or processes. On systemic or individual level.
	Explorative Scenario (Utforskande Scenario)	Scenarios designed to explore possible outcomes of future situations.
	Predictive Scenario (Förutseende scenario)	Scenarios designed to predict outcomes of future situations.
Scenario Components	LARP Scenario (Lajv)	Recreational and improvised scenarios where participants embody roles in a fictional setting.
	Structured vs Emergent (Strukturerat eller emergent narrativ)	Predetermined story-lines and event sequence or participantdriven outcomes.
	Pacing Mechanisms (Temposättande mekanismer)	Methods such as time compression or event sequencing to maintain engagement and flow throughout the scenario.
	Narrative (Narrativ)	A story that runs through and contextualises the scenario.
	Introduction (Inledande narrativ)	Initial setup, including time, place, and environmental conditions.
	Mood-setting texts (Stämningstexter)	Atmosphere-setting texts used for immersion.
	Injects (Inspel)	Planned events or stimuli introduced during the scenario to guide progression or test responses.
	Event (Moment)	An isolated temporal snapshot containing specific actions or shifts in the scenario
	Intrigues (Intriger)	Personalized goals, secrets, or backstories to enhance engagement.
	Safety Systems (Säkerhetssystem)	Protocols ensuring participant safety and comfort, including broms, bryt, and trafikljussystemet.
Temporal Dynamics	Off/Inline	Terms distinguishing in-character (inline) actions from out-of-character (off) interactions.
	Timeline (Tidsförlopp)	Temporal nature of the scenario. Chronological, non-linear, or real-time.
	Starting point (Startpunkt)	The initial event or context participants are exposed to.
Immersion Mechanisms	End Point (Slutpunkt)	Concluding event, condition or action signaling the end of the scenario.
	Engagement Triggers (Inlevelseskapande element)	Elements like videos, props, rituals, and more that create immersion and interest.
	Bleed	Actions, events and emotions experienced during the scenario that impact the real world and vice versa, impacted by immersion.

Categories	Terms	Definitions
	Safety Mechanisms (Säkerhetsmekanismer)	Tools ensure participants' well-being during intense scenarios.
	World-Building (Världsbyggande)	Creating a cohesive setting through language, rituals, and physical elements.
	Props and Costumes (Rekvisita och Kostymer)	Tangible items enhancing the sense of realism.
	Symbolic Indicators (Symboliska Indikatorer)	Markers for in-game or out-of-game states (e.g., hand gestures, item tags).
Design Attributes	Realism (Verklighetstroget)	Degree to which the scenario mimics real-world conditions.
	Simulated realism (Simulerad realism)	Abstract or theoretical realism (e.g., maps, discussions, communication patterns and modes)
	Physical realism (Fysisk realism)	Physical dimensions and tangible elements (e.g., props, environments).
	Believable realism (Trovärdighet)	How probable and realistic the narrative, scenario, events and other processes are. Impacts immersion.
	Control Level (Kontrollnivå)	Directed Scenario: Controlled with predefined outcomes; Dynamic scenario: Flexible, improvised.
	Spatial Complexity (Rumslig komplexitet)	Degree of physical dispersion or integration of participants. Amount of participant groups and physical locations.
	Complexity (Komplexitetsnivå)	Level of detail and resource intensity, including participants, resources, and time structure, events.
Roles	Participants (Deltagare)	Individuals participating in the scenario through predefined or improvised roles.
	Organizers (Arrangörer)	Those responsible for creating, managing and executing the scenario.
	Game Master/ Facilitator (Spelledare/ Övningsledare)	Facilitator introducing events or guiding participants during the scenario.
	Counterpart/ Adversary (Motspelare/ Figurant)	Scripted roles played to enrich the scenario or drive specific actions.
Evaluation and Outcomes	Key Performance Indicators (Mätpunkter)	Criteria or benchmarks for assessing outcomes.
	Scoring System (Poängsystem)	A quantitative evaluation framework.
	After-Action Review	Summaries or Reflections on what occurred during the scenario.
Logistics and Tools	Multi-Modality Tools	Use of props, digital platforms, and live actors for layered scenario experiences.
	Documentation Tools (Dokumentationsverktyg)	Platforms like Word, Excel and so on to organize the scenario and how the scenario is documented as it is acted out
	Digital Tools (Digitala Verktyg)	Platforms for communication, mapping, and real-time adjustments, designing scenarios interactions and environments